

CERTIFICATION FOR DESIGN:
RESHAPING THE TESTING
PYRAMID

Testing and progressive failure modelling of a wind turbine blade spar cap/web joint substructure

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- **Load response** of composite structures is **scale and stress state dependent** (in-situ effect, manufacturing defects, multi-material interactions, etc.)
- True performance can only be evaluated **on the substructural scale** accounting for **multiaxial loading**
- **Full-field imaging** has the potential to capture **complex mechanical response**
- Testing and modelling at the substructure scale can lead to **more efficient structures**, while reducing **time to market and cost of the certification process** by reducing number of tests
- Substructural scale experiments needed for **validation of virtual testing techniques**, enabling their **deployment on higher levels of the testing pyramid**

Multiaxial substructures testing

FE prediction

Load case definition

Detailed test design

Multi-camera set-up

(Laux et al., Eng Struct, 2025.)

DIC experimental results

MatchID

Metrology Beyond Colors

DIC experimental results

MatchID Metrology Beyond Colors

MatchID Metrology Beyond Colors

Finite element model & virtual DIC

Just before failure ($P_1 = 32.5\text{kN}$)

Step towards "like-for-like" comparison

Error map statistics

- Mean errors within +/- 100 $\mu\epsilon$
- Standard deviation increases with load
- Change of slope indicates damage onset?

- Building error in shear strains -> Needs further investigation
- Change of slope indicates damage onset?

Biaxial web laminates

Wood web core

Wood fillet

Delamination of “overlaminates” subjected to mixed mode loading

Nonlinear failure model shows good agreement. Validation in progress.

- **Multi-camera DIC** set-up successfully **captured complex substructure deformation**
- Mitigation measures against the effect of **heat waves** improved quality of DIC results
- Full-field imaging and data fusion with FE results enables comprehensive and quantitative **FE model validation**
- MatchID Finite Element Deformation tool to generate “virtual DIC” images is a step towards “**like-for-like**” comparisons, enabling more rigorous FE model assessment in the elastic material response
- Multiaxial substructure test was able to **characterise critical failure mode of WTB spar cap/web joint**
- **Integrated testing and modelling** at the substructures scale has the potential to provide **a route to validation for complex virtual testing techniques**

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Thank you for your attention. Any questions?

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Integrated testing and modelling of substructures using full-field imaging and data fusion

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